

A Study of Purchase & Post-Purchase Behaviour of the Customer in Relation to Patanjali Products**Arvind Kumar, Assistant Professor,****Department of Commerce, I.P. PG College, Bulandshahr****ABSTRACT**

Customers are value maximizers. Perception is a person's understanding or a viewpoint about things around him, which ultimately results in positive or negative satisfaction. Likewise, Satisfaction is a person's feeling or disappointment, resulting from comparison of a product that is perceived and actual performance in relation to his or her expectations. This paper tries to study Customer Perception in relation to products of Patanjali Ayurved Ltd, one of the fastest emerging brand in India and world over. The study also intends to examine product range, the customer's spending patterns, buying behaviour, factors affecting their purchase, post purchase behaviour of the customer in relation to Patanjali products and ultimately to analyse the overall satisfaction level of Patanjali Customers. It is seen that Patanjali is able to capture more than 70% of the market in general. With the growth rate of 130%, Patanjali has expanded like never before capturing local, national and international markets, and has officially surpassed even the strongest FMCG giants. This is mainly due to ethical conduct of its founder. Use of Ayurveda and technological migrations into its R&D cell has enabled it to gain trustworthiness, support and loyalty from its customers. Potential customers in this generation are becoming more concerned about their health and determined to enhance their standard of living, as shown by their preference for products that protect their health while offering complete satisfaction. A Customer will go through a purchasing behaviour process in order to purchase a product. This research paper aims at finding the factors influencing the Customer buying behaviour towards Patanjali products. The analysis of the data shows that factors Quality, Freshness, Flavour, Colour, Brand Image and Packing have more impact on the customer buying behaviour towards Patanjali products.

Keywords: Brand loyalty, Quality, Buying Behaviour, Perception, Satisfaction, Patanjali.

INTRODUCTION

A large portion of the user is satisfied from Patanjali products. It may be because of reasonable price of the product. It may be due to ability of the product to cure their health problem. The satisfaction brings in the retention of customer. Similarly, Patanjali has been very successful in their consumer awareness programmes reaching wide target audience. Credibility and reliability of Patanjali products and their good quality becomes major buying motives among customers. Patanjali is enjoying the advantageous position in market through spirituality element involved in its products. It has crossed revenues of Rs. 10,000 Crores, and Acharya Balkrishna enters Forbes Rich List with \$2.5 billion. Patanjali Ayurveda Limited, with its registered office in New Delhi, was established in 2006 under the Company Act of 1956. "Swami Ramdev Ji" and "Acharya Balakrishna" established Patanjali Ayurveda Ltd. in 2006 with vision and mission as "Keeping nationalism, Ayurveda and Yog as our pillars, we are committed to create a healthier society and country. To raise the pride and glory of the world, we are geared up to serve people by bringing the

blessings of nature into their lives.” The aim and vision were to combine science and ancient Ayurvedic knowledge to create Ayurvedic products that were scientifically accepted. This approach starts with an analysis of ancient Indian scientific texts, then moves on to the collection and discovery of effective and authentic herbs, and finally to safety testing to produce a new product that is effective. The business concentrates on cultivating a variety of endangered herbs on its own. The Divya Yog Mandir Trust and Patanjali Yog Peeth, which ensures and monitors the quality of the herbs used in the production of the goods, carry out the mission. The principles of Good Industrial Practices (GMP) are strictly practised in the manufacturing plant. The company prides itself on being environmentally friendly. It also has a website called “**Patanjaliayurved.net**”, which is the official Patanjali Products online store. Customers are just a click away from the company's commitment to delivering high-quality goods. Along with delivering high-quality goods, the organisation is committed to providing excellent service and realtime assistance. Patanjali offers a wide range of products, including food, cosmetics, medicine all at reasonable prices. Patanjali Ayurved Limited has unique project teams working on Total Quality Management (TQM) projects, with the aim of making quality a way of life. This ensures consistent batch-to-batch continuity and ensures that their customers receive the same high-quality products regardless of where they buy them. Customer satisfaction is the aim of all economic activity. It deals with the characteristics of human behaviour and affects the buying behaviour of customers. It is a method, which helps to study the needs of customers. It helps in knowing about the way customer think and perceive about the brand and its products. Patanjali Ayurved Limited manufactures over 900 items, including 45 types of cosmetics and 30 types of food, with the needs and satisfaction of its customers as a top priority. Patanjali's product line caters to almost every Customer group. Patanjali's strategy, according to various media reports, is to concentrate on the consistency, affordability, and purity of the goods, which has proven to be effective. The main Customer base for Patanjali is Baba Ramdev's followers, but the interesting part is the popularity of Patanjali products among non-followers. The increasing health problems that are lifestyle related and the controversies of the top brand like Nestle for its product Maggi, Cadbury, Coco – Cola etc. really helped in strengthening the brand hold on its customer base and attracting the new customers. Patanjali is also expanding its customer base in metropolitan cities. After building a strong customer base in Tier – 2 and Tier – 3 cities, the aim is to move to Tier – 1. The strong customer base in small cities results in word of mouth, which will increase awareness of brand's quality, purity and authenticity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 “Pooja Agarwal, C. K. Tiwari (2019)”, with a 5% degree of significance, their analysis on “Customer Purchase Behaviour for Patanjali Brand found that there is no substantial difference between the age groups primarily below 20, 21 – 30, 31 – 40, and 40 – 50, embracing the null hypothesis” (Pooja Agarwal, C. K. Tiwari). In the case of gender and purchasing behaviour, they support the null hypothesis, claiming that there is no substantial difference in the purchasing behaviour of male and female customers. [1]

1.2 “J. Malarvizhi, T. Chitra Devi (2018)”, the investigator attempted to discover the marketing methods used by the Ayurvedic to sell their Patanjali products in the report on consumer satisfaction with Patanjali products. The majority of respondents cited “the lack of a marketplace/shop for selling Patanjali products” as their primary concern. [2]

1.3 “Ruchi Jaggi, Munmun Ghosh (2017)”, there were 112 respondents in the survey on Customer perceptions of Patanjali Products - an Analytical Study, 60 of whom were females and 52 of whom were males. Patanjali's successful marketing strategy has had a significant impact on the perception of its goods and has helped to build a positive picture of the company. As a result, Patanjali's commercials are the third most widely broadcast on Indian television.

1.4 “S Anupriya (2017)”, “Customers of this millennium have become more concerned about their wellbeing and inclined toward preserving the quality of life, which is reflected in the preferential consumption of these goods, according to a report on Customer preference and perception towards Patanjali products.” It protects the good state of health and also provide maximum satisfaction. The Customer satisfaction can be derived when they compare the actual performance of product with the performance expected by them after usage.

1.5 “Subbulakshmi and Geethamani (2017)”, in the study on customer’s perception for cosmetic in Patanjali Products With Reference To Tirupur City” shows that the FMCG are the products sold at a faster rate and relatively low price. Patanjali has emerged as one of the top competitors of FMCG products in the market. The quality benefits that a brand offers influence the customer's choice and consumption of a product for that brand, especially in the case of eatables and cosmetics. Customer satisfaction can be determined by comparing the product's actual performance to the performance they predicted after use.

1.6 “Jignesh Valand and Anand. Parikshit Kelkar (2018)”, “An Empirical Study on Customers Perception Regarding Patanjali Tooth Paste in Anand City” the study revealed that Customer (who uses a product or service) is the centre point in the market. Now days Patanjali provides wide varieties of choice in terms of toothpaste. The study mainly focus on knowing the customer's preference towards Patanjali as a brand. It also focus on knowing the minds of people (who use the product or service) and the products quality influencing the customers especially in terms of toothpaste. [7]

1.7 “A report in Business Standard (Rakshit, 2016)”, “according to the study, Patanjali has continuously advertised its goods, concentrating on the consistency and purity of the product in order to dispel customer concerns about its products. Furthermore, it has managed to keep the costs down. Above all, it has consistently conveyed the unique characteristics of its goods as well as their reasonable price. For a pack of 250g, Patanjali honey is advertised as being 43 percent cheaper than the competitor's product (Dabur honey). Dabur's 500 g honey pack costs 199 rupees, while Patanjali's honey 500 g pack costs 135, which is 32 percent less.” [9]

1.8 “According to Khanna Rupali (2015)”, “in her study customer Perception towards Brand: A Study on Patanjali explained to us the factor influencing the Patanjali brand. The Customer perception towards a brand depends on the satisfaction of the customer after using the product. In the study it was found that majority of the users are satisfied with Patanjali products, which in turn help the company in customer retention.”

1.9 “According to Nagaraju and Thejaswini (2014)”, “their study Customer perception analysis and Market awareness towards environment friendly FMCG products analyses the fact that the customers give more preference and importance to environment friendly FMCG products, as they

are very healthy and environment cautious. Patanjali understood the customer preference and rightly marketed its products in the same category.” [11]

1.10 “According to Ganesh and Rosario John (2015)”, the study, “Customers perception towards Brand loyalty of FMCG products” in which he explain that the satisfaction creates brand loyalty after using the product by the customers. The product knowledge and awareness play an important role in creating the brand image and loyalty in the minds of customers.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Customers are the shareholders of the marketplace, and their desire to enforce satisfaction has a significant impact on economic market transition. The accuracy in determining what customers are aware of and their purchasing desires, as well as delivering goods that meet these needs would help the industry enrich and accelerate market growth. Given that the customer is the king of every company, it is vital to comprehend customer demands, product preferences, and needs and desires. No company will prosper without a comprehensive understanding of customer behaviour. The main goal of this project is to learn more about how people feel about Patanjali products. This research is primarily concerned with the various factors that influence a Customer's purchasing decision. Social, psychological, and personal factors all play a role. This research aids in determining the customer buying behaviour and the satisfaction of customers are with the brand. Understanding customer attitudes and purchasing motivations through company brand image is also relevant in understanding their buying behaviour.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess customer perception towards the “Patanjali” brand using survey via questionnaires.
- To learn about the factors that customer consider when purchasing “Patanjali” products.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is fundamental in nature and concentrates on the Patanjali brand. The data for the research was both primary and secondary, and the analysis approach was quantitative. To begin, the primary data is gathered via a questionnaire. Closed ended, ranking, Likert scale, and multiple-choice questions are among the types of questions used. The data is collected using convenient sampling. Our survey data will consist primarily of people between the ages of 18 and 40, with varying levels of income and educational qualifications. The data will be collected using questions that cover factors such as price, brand, quality, availability, and other factors that influence Customer psychological behaviour and will help us understand Customer attitudes and purchasing behaviour toward Patanjali products. Secondary information is gathered from a variety of magazines and brochures. To gain an understanding of past approaches, articles and academic papers are reviewed.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

H0 = There is no relationship between **quality, freshness, flavour, colour, brand image, reasonable**

price, availability, advertisement or offers, retailers influence, packing and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products.

H1 = There is relationship between **quality** and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products.

H2 = There is relationship between **freshness** and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products.

H3 = There is relationship between **flavour** and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products.

H4 = There is relationship between **colour** and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products.

H5 = There is relationship between **brand image** and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products

H6 = There is relationship between **reasonable price** and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products.

H7 = There is relationship between **availability** and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products.

H8 = There is relationship between **advertisement or offers** and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products.

H9 = There is relationship between **retailers influence** and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products.

H10 = There is relationship between **packing** and Customer buying habits when it comes to “Patanjali” products.

FINDINGS

The findings of the study indicate that a number of significant factors influences a customer’s purchasing decision.

- Quality, freshness, flavour, colour, brand image, advertisement or offers and packing emerged as the key factors that has influenced the buying behaviour of customers towards Patanjali products. The product origin (37.30%), Lab recommendations (27.10%) and Baba Ramdev (22.00%) influence the trustworthiness of the product among the respondents.

- The study also reveals that the most used Patanjali products are personal care (36.70%) followed by Health care (26.70%) and Grocery (21.70%) mostly on daily purpose (30.50%) followed by once in a week (28.80). The findings of personal care product is similar to the study of “**Gurmeet Kaur(2016)**”. People accept Patanjali's products because of their herbal nature, good quality, and fair price when compared to other MNCs, according to the findings of the study.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research we can conclude that most of the major consumer of Patanjali products are in the age group of 18-25 and the majority of them are postgraduates. We can also conclude that Quality, freshness, flavour, colour, brand image, advertisement or offers and packing are the key factors that influence the buying behaviour of customers towards Patanjali products and the company should focus on these factors. The conclusion is similar to which focus on conveying quality of product to people. Personal care is the most used Patanjali product and beverages and

household were the least used. However, because Patanjali is expanding its business, it is recommended that it concentrate on personal care, healthcare, and grocery items.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Based on the study, flavour and colour of the product have impact on the customer buying behaviour, but the ratings for these factors are average. Hence, the company should focus on improving these factors.
- Advertisements and offers drives most of the sales for Patanjali products as it influence the customer buying behaviour, but the ratings for this factor is also average. Hence, the company should frequently announce offers and discounts.
- The company should focus more on developing the personal care, healthcare and grocery products, which is considered the most used products as per the study.

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